

IOHEXOL INDUCED TOXIC EPIDERMAL NECROLYSIS - A RARE CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- Toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN) is a rare, life-threatening drug-induced skin disease also known as Lyell's syndrome and is a common cause of significant skin and mucous membrane disintegration. Thus, this case of TEN induced by Iohexol has been found to be rare in relevant scientific literature. **Case details-** An 83-year-old male patient diagnosed with Pancreatic pseudocyst got admitted in HIMS Surgery department 2 months ago and was advised CECT abdomen scan, during which the patient was given Contrast Iohexol. Two days following which the patient developed erythema over the back which gradually extended to axilla and upper limbs. Multiple erosions of various sizes and shapes present on the back and upper limbs and on genitalia with conjunctival congestion and haemorrhagic crests on both eyelids and lips. Provisional diagnosis of Toxic epidermal

necrolysis was made by Dermatologist, and patient was put on Inj. dexamethasone, Inj. Chlorpheniramine malate, Tab Cyclosporine and antibiotics (Inj. Piperacillin + Tazobactam). The rashes started to subside after 8 days of supportive treatment. **Conclusion:** As there are very few reports of iohexol-induced TEN, we present a case of TEN triggered by the non-ionic iodinated contrast medium iohexol, with the aim of improving awareness and helping to prevent iohexol-induced TEN.

KEYWORDS: Iohexol, Adverse drug reaction, Toxic epidermal necrolysis.

INTRODUCTION

Toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN) is a rare, life-threatening drug-induced skin disease also known as Lyell's syndrome and is a common cause of significant skin and mucous membrane disintegration.^[1] The clinical characteristic of TEN is marked skin detachment due to extensive keratinocyte death that is related to mucosal involvement. The distinguishing characteristics of this pathology are erythema, epidermal detachment that appears as blisters, and patches of denuded skin.^[2] The administration of pharmaceutical drugs is the primary cause of SJS/TEN in the majority of cases, this case of TEN induced by Iohexol has been found to be rare in relevant scientific literature.^[5]

CASE DETAILS

A 83-year-old male patient diagnosed with Pancreatic pseudocyst got admitted in HIMS Surgery department 2 months ago and was advised CECT abdomen scan, during which the patient was given Contrast Iohexol. Two days following which the patient developed erythema over the back which gradually extended to axilla and upper limbs. Multiple erosions of various sizes and shapes present on the back and upper limbs and on genitalia with conjunctival congestion and haemorrhagic crusts on both eyelids and lips. As the lesions didn't resolve patient was referred and got admitted in Dermatology ward, Provisional diagnosis of Toxic epidermal necrolysis was made by Dermatologist.

LOCAL EXAMINATION (by dermatologist)

Haemorrhagic crusts present on B/L eyelids, and lower lip. Multiple extending erosions (some coalescing) of various sizes and shapes present on the back with positive Nikolsky sign. Hair, Nail, Oral and Genital mucosa – Normal.

DIAGNOSIS: Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN)

TREATMENT: Inj. dexamethasone, Inj.Chlorphenaramine malate, Tab Cyclosporine and antibiotic (Inj.Piperacillin + Tazobactam).

Hemorrhagic crusts and Multiple erosions of various sizes and shapes on eyelids, lips, back and other parts of the body.

The rashes slowly started to subside after 8 days of supportive treatment.

Patient discharged with advice on proper diet, continuation on supportive treatment and regular follow up.

Follow Up - didn't show any new lesions and the existing lesions started to resolve. Later patient got admitted back to surgery ward and got operated on for the Pancreatic pseudocyst.

DISCUSSION

Limited evidence has shown an association between the use of iodinated contrast and the development of SJS and TEN.^[2]

Walsh et al. 2019; reported 11 cases of iodinated contrast-induced SJS and/or TEN. Of these 11 cases, symptoms had occurred 30 minutes to 3 days after administration, with three of the patients died.^[2] Patients with TEN had an increased mortality.² Shakeel et al 2021; reported a case that had associated the use of parental and oral contrast as the cause of a patient's SJS or TEN.^[4]

The mechanism of SJS and TEN is unclear but most likely results from a delayed T-cell reaction, with additional evidence implicating genetic susceptibilities and cytotoxicity.^[1] The Naranjo adverse drug reaction probability scale is a standardized method for assessing the causal agent of an adverse drug reaction.^[3] Using this scale, contrast has a score of 7, which is considered "probable" and is higher than that of the other medications at exposure.^[3]

Our patient had presented with SJS, after the administration of iodinated contrast. Other possibilities, such as HSV, VZV, and mycoplasma infections, were ruled out. A diagnosis of generalized bullous fixed drug eruption (GBFDE) could also be considered, given the similarity in presentations that also ruled out by dermatologists.

Management includes supportive care, including wound care, fluid and electrolyte management, pain control and to prevent risk of infection by using antibiotics. Emerging evidence has supported the use of immune modulating agents, such as cyclosporine for adjunctive treatment.^[5]

CONCLUSION

As there are very few reports on Iohexol induced TEN, this case report will help in understanding the importance and help in preventing such events in the future.

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REFERENCES

1. Pasternak JJ, Williamson EE. Clinical pharmacology, uses, and adverse reactions of iodinated contrast agents: a primer for the non-radiologist. *Mayo Clin Proc.*, 2012; 87(4): 390–402.

2. Tasker F, Fleming H, McNeill G, Creamer D, Walsh S. Contrast media and cutaneous reactions. Part 2: delayed hypersensitivity reactions to iodinated contrast media. *Clin Exp Dermatol.*, 2019; 44(8): 844–60.
3. Naranjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM, Sandor P, Ruiz I, Roberts EA, et al. A method for estimating the probability of adverse drug reactions. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.*, 1981; 30: 239-45.
4. Pop M, Hemenway A, Shakeel F. Probable parenteral and oral contrast-induced Steven Johnson syndrome/toxic epidermal necrolysis. *Am J Emerg Med.*, 2021; 45: 684. e5-6.
5. Zimmermann S, Sekula P, Venhoff M, Motschall E, Knaus J, Schumacher M, et al. Systemic immunomodulating therapies for Stevens-Johnson syndrome and toxic epidermal necrolysis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Dermatol.*, 2017; 153: 514-22.